

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 68

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 68

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 68:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David. A Song.</p>	<p>Psa. 68:1 לְמִנְצַח לְדָוִד מִזְמוֹר</p>
<p>Psa. 68:1 ¹Let ^aGod arise, ²let His enemies be scattered,</p>	<p>שִׁיר : ² יִקּוּם אֱלֹהִים יִפּוּצוּ אוֹיְבָיו וַיִּנּוּסוּ מִשְׁנֵאָיו</p>
<p>And ³let those who hate Him flee before Him.</p>	<p>מִפְּנֵיו : ³ כְּהַנְדִּיף עָשָׁן תִּהְדָּף כְּהַיָּס דּוֹנֵג מִפְּנֵי־אֵשׁ</p>
<p>² As ^asmoke is driven away, <i>so</i> drive <i>them</i> away;</p>	<p>יֵאבְדוּ רְשָׁעִים מִפְּנֵי אֱלֹהִים : ⁴ וַצְדִיקִים יִשְׂמְחוּ יַעֲלִצוּ לִפְנֵי אֱלֹהִים וַיִּשְׂשׂוּ בְשִׂמְחָה : ⁵ שִׁירוּ אֶל־אֱלֹהִים וַמְרוּ שְׁמוֹ סֹלוֹ לְרֶכֶב</p>
<p>As ^bwax melts before the fire, <i>So</i> let the ^cwicked perish before God.</p>	<p>בְּעָרְבוֹת בְּיָהּ שְׁמוֹ וְעֵלְזוּ לִפְנֵיו : ⁶ אֲבִי יִתּוּמִים וְדַיָּן אֶלְמָנוֹת אֱלֹהִים בְּמַעֲוֹן קָדְשׁוֹ : ⁷ אֱלֹהִים אֲמוֹשֵׁיב יַחֲדָיִם אֲסִירִים בְּכוֹשְׁרוֹת אֶךְ סוֹרְרִים שְׁכֵנוֹ צְחִיחָה : ⁸ אֱלֹהִים בְּצִאתְךָ לִפְנֵי עַמְּךָ בְּצַעְדְּךָ בִישִׁימוֹן סִלָּה : ⁹ אֶרֶץ רַעֲשָׁה אֶרֶץ־שָׁמַיִם נָטְפוּ מִפְּנֵי אֱלֹהִים זֶה סִינַי</p>
<p>³ But let the ^arighteous be glad; let them exult before God;</p>	<p>Yes, let them rejoice with gladness.</p>
<p>Yes, let them rejoice with gladness.</p>	<p>⁴ Sing to God, ^asing praises to His name;</p>
<p>⁴ Sing to God, ^asing praises to His name;</p>	<p>^{1b}Lift up <i>a song</i> for Him who ^crides through the deserts,</p>
<p>^{1b}Lift up <i>a song</i> for Him who ^crides through the deserts,</p>	<p>Whose ^dname is ²the LORD, and exult before Him.</p>
<p>Whose ^dname is ²the LORD, and exult before Him.</p>	<p>Psa. 68:5 A ^afather of the fatherless and a ^bjudge ¹for the widows,</p>
<p>Psa. 68:5 A ^afather of the fatherless and a ^bjudge ¹for the widows,</p>	<p>Is God in His ^choly habitation.</p>
<p>Is God in His ^choly habitation.</p>	<p>⁶ God ^{1a}makes a home for the lonely;</p>
<p>⁶ God ^{1a}makes a home for the lonely;</p>	<p>He ^bleads out the prisoners into prosperity,</p>
<p>He ^bleads out the prisoners into prosperity,</p>	<p>Only ^cthe rebellious dwell in a parched land.</p>
<p>Only ^cthe rebellious dwell in a parched land.</p>	<p>Psa. 68:7 O God, when You ^awent forth before Your people,</p>
<p>Psa. 68:7 O God, when You ^awent forth before Your people,</p>	<p>When You ^bmarched through the wilderness, ¹Selah.</p>
<p>When You ^bmarched through the wilderness, ¹Selah.</p>	<p></p>

⁸ The ^aearth quaked;
 The ^bheavens also dropped *rain* at
 the presence of God;
¹Sinai itself *quaked* at the presence
 of God, the God of Israel.
⁹ You ^ashed abroad a plentiful rain,
 O God;
 You confirmed Your inheritance
 when it was ¹parched.
¹⁰ Your creatures settled in it;
 You ^aprovided in Your goodness
 for the poor, O God.

Psa. 68:11 The Lord gives the
¹command;

The ^awomen who proclaim the
good tidings are a great host:

¹² “^aKings of armies flee, they flee,
 And she who remains at home
 will ^bdivide the spoil!”

¹³ ¹When you lie down ^aamong the
²sheepfolds,

You are like the wings of a dove
 covered with silver,
 And its pinions with glistening
 gold.

¹⁴ When the Almighty ^ascattered the
 kings ¹there,
 It was snowing in ^bZalmon.

Psa. 68:15 A ^{1a}mountain of God is the
 mountain of Bashan;

A mountain *of many* peaks is the
 mountain of Bashan.

¹⁶ Why do you look with envy, O
 mountains with *many* peaks,

At the mountain which God has
^adesired for His abode?

Surely ^bthe LORD will dwell *there*
 forever.

מִפְּנֵי אֱלֹהִים אֶלְהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל :
¹⁰ גִּשְׁמֵם נִדְּבֹת הַנִּיחַ אֱלֹהִים
 נַחֲלָתְךָ וְנִלְאָה אֶתְּהָ
 כֹּונֵנְתָהּ : ¹¹ תִּיתְךָ יִשְׁבוּ-בָהּ
 תִּכֵּין בְּטֹובְתְךָ לְעַנִּי
 אֱלֹהִים : ¹² אֶלְנִי יִתֵּן-אֶמֶר
 הַמְּבֹשְׂרוֹת צָבָא רָב : ¹³
 מִלְכֵי צָבָאוֹת יִדְּרוּן יִדְּרוּן
 וְנֹוֹת בַּיִת תִּתְחַלֵּק שָׁלָל : ¹⁴
 אִם-תִּשְׁכְּבוּן בֵּין שְׁפָתַיִם
 כִּנְפֵי יוֹנָה נַחֲפָה בַכֶּסֶף
 וְאֶבְרוֹתֶיהָ בִּירְקֶרֶק חֲרוֹץ :
¹⁵ בְּפֶרֶשׁ שִׁדֵי מְלָכִים בָּהּ
 תִּשְׁלַג בְּצִלְמוֹן : ¹⁶ הַר-
 אֱלֹהִים הַר-בְּשָׁן הַר גִּבְנֵנִים
 הַר-בְּשָׁן : ¹⁷ לָמָּה אֶתְרַצְדּוּן
 הָרִים גִּבְנֵנִים הָהָר חֲמֹד
 אֱלֹהִים לְשִׁבְתוֹ אֶרֶץ-יְהוָה
 יִשְׁכֵן לְנִצַּח : ¹⁸ רֶכֶב אֱלֹהִים
 רַב־תַּיִם אֶלְפֵי שִׁנְאָן אֶדְנִי
 בָּם סִינִי בַקֶּדֶשׁ : ¹⁹ עָלִיתָ
 לְמָרוֹם אֲשֶׁר־שָׁבִי לְקַחְתָּ
 מִתַּנּוֹת בְּאָדָם וְאֶרֶץ סוּרְרִים

¹⁷ The ^achariots of God are
¹myriads, ^bthousands upon thousands;
²The Lord is among them *as at*
Sinai, in holiness.

¹⁸ You have ^aascended on high, You
have ^bled captive *Your* captives;
You have received gifts among
men,

Even *among* the rebellious also,
that ¹the LORD God may dwell *there*.

Psa. 68:19 Blessed be the Lord, who
daily ^abears our burden,

^bThe God *who* is our Salvation.

Selah.

²⁰ God is to us a ^aGod of
deliverances;

And ^bto ¹GOD the Lord belong
escapes ²from death.

²¹ Surely God will ^ashatter the head
of His enemies,

The hairy crown of him who goes
on in his guilty deeds.

²² The Lord ¹said, “I will bring *them*
back from Bashan.

I will bring *them* back from the
depths of the sea;

²³ That ¹“your foot may shatter *them*
in blood,

The tongue of your ^bdogs *may have*
its portion from *your* enemies.”

Psa. 68:24 They have seen

“Your ¹procession, O God,

The ¹procession of my God, my
King, ^{2b}into the sanctuary.

²⁵ The ^asingers went on, the
musicians after *them*,

¹In the midst of the ^bmaidens
beating tambourines.

²⁶ “Bless God in the congregations,

לְשֹׁכֵן אֱלֹהִים : ²⁰ בְּרִוְךְ
אֲדֹנָי יוֹם יוֹם יַעֲמֹס-לָנוּ
הָאֵל יִשׁוּעֵתָנוּ סֵלָה : ²¹ הָאֵל
אֲדֹנָי אֵל לְמוֹשָׁעוֹת וְלִיהוֹנָה
אֲדֹנָי לְמִנּוֹת תּוֹצְאוֹת : ²² אֲדֹ-
נָי אֱלֹהִים יִמְחֶץ רֹאשׁ אֲבִיבֵי
קֶדְקֶד שֹׁעַר מִתְהַלֵּךְ
בְּאַשְׁמֵיָו : ²³ אָמַר אֲדֹנָי
מִבֶּשֶׁן אָשִׁיב אָשִׁיב מִמִּצְלוֹת
יָם : ²⁴ לְמַעַן אֶתְמַחֶץ רִגְלֶךָ
בְּדָם לְשׁוֹן כָּל־בֵּיךְ מֵאֲיִבִים
מִנְהוּ : ²⁵ רָאוּ הַלְיִכוֹתֶיךָ
אֱלֹהִים הַלְיִכוֹת אֵלַי מִלְכֵי
בְּקֶדְשׁ : ²⁶ קֶדְמוֹ שָׂרִים אֲחֵר
נִגְנִים בְּתוֹךְ עֲלָמוֹת
תּוֹפְפוֹת : ²⁷ בְּמִקְהֵלוֹת בְּרִכּוֹ
אֱלֹהִים יְהוָה מִמִּקְדָּו
יִשְׂרָאֵל : ²⁸ נֶשֶׁם בְּנֵי־מִן אֶצְעִיר
רוּחַ שָׂרֵי יְהוּדָה רִגְמָתָם
שָׂרֵי זָבְלוֹן שָׂרֵי נֶפְתָלַי : ²⁹
צִנּוֹת אֱלֹהֶיךָ עֲנֶךָ עוֹנֶה
אֱלֹהִים זֹו פִּעֲלָתָ לָנוּ : ³⁰
מִהֵיכָלְךָ עַל-יְרוּשָׁלַם לְךָ

Even the LORD, *you who are* of the ^bfountain of Israel.

²⁷ There is ^aBenjamin, the ¹youngest, ²ruling them,

The princes of Judah *in* their throng,

The princes of ^bZebulun, the princes of Naphtali.

Psa. 68:28 ¹Your God has ^acommanded your strength;

Show Yourself strong, O God, ^bwho have acted ²on our behalf.

²⁹ ¹Because of Your temple at Jerusalem

^aKings will bring gifts to You.

³⁰ Rebuke the ^abeasts ¹in the reeds, The herd of ^bbulls with the calves of the peoples,

Trampling under foot the pieces of silver;

He has ^cscattered the peoples who delight in war.

³¹ Envoys will come out of ^aEgypt; ¹Ethiopia will quickly stretch out her hands to God.

Psa. 68:32 Sing to God, O ^akingdoms of the earth,

^bSing praises to the Lord, Selah.

³³ To Him who ^arides upon the ¹highest heavens, which are from ancient times;

Behold, ^cHe ²speaks forth with His voice, a ^amighty voice.

³⁴ ^aAscribe strength to God; His majesty is over Israel And ^bHis strength is in the ¹skies.

³⁵ ¹O God, *You are* ^aawesome from Your ²sanctuary.

יִבְיִלוּ מְלָכִים שִׁי : ³¹ גְּעֵר
תִּתְּ קָנָה עֶרְת אֲבִירִים |
בְּעִגְלֵי עַמִּים מִתְרַפֵּס
בְּרִצֵּי-כֶסֶף בְּזֶר עַמִּים
קָרְבוֹת יִחַפְּצוּ : ³² יִאֲתִיּוּ
חֲשֹׁמֵי־מִנִּי מִצְרִים כּוֹשׁ
תִּרְיֵץ יָדָיו לֵאלֹהִים : ³³
מִמְלְכוֹת הָאָרֶץ שִׁירוּ
לֵאלֹהִים זַמְרוּ אֲדֹנָי סֵלָה :
³⁴ לָרֶכֶב בְּשָׁמַי שְׁמֵי-קָדָם הֵן
יִתֵן בְּקוֹלוֹ קוֹל עֹז : ³⁵ תִּנְנוּ עֹז
לֵאלֹהִים עַל-יִשְׂרָאֵל וּגְאֻתוֹ
וְעֹז בְּשִׁתְּקִים : ³⁶ נֹרָא
אֱלֹהִים מִמְּקַדְּשֵׁיךָ אֵל
יִשְׂרָאֵל הוּא נִתֵן אֵז
וְתַעֲצֹמוֹת לָעַם בְּרוּךְ
אֱלֹהִים :

<p>The God of Israel Himself ^b gives strength and power to the people. Blessed be God!</p>	
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References

Psalm 68:1

¹Or *God shall*

²Or *His enemies shall*

³Or *those who hate Him shall*

^aNum 10:35; Ps 12:5; 132:8

Psalm 68:2

^aPs 37:20; Is 9:18; Hos 13:3

^bPs 22:14; 97:5; Mic 1:4

^cPs 9:3; 37:20; 80:16

Psalm 68:3

^aPs 32:11; 64:10; 97:12

Psalm 68:4

¹Or *Cast up* a highway

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 66:2

^bIs 57:14; 62:10

^cDeut 33:26; Ps 18:10; 68:33; Is 40:3

^dEx 6:3; Ps 83:18

Psalm 68:5

¹Lit *of*

^aPs 10:14; 146:9

^bDeut 10:18

^cDeut 26:15

Psalm 68:6

¹Lit *makes the solitary to dwell in a house*

^aPs 107:4-7; 113:9

^bPs 69:33; 102:20; 107:10, 14; 146:7; Acts 12:7; 16:26

^cPs 78:17; 107:34, 40

Psalm 68:7

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aEx 13:21; Ps 78:14; Hab 3:13

^bJudg 5:4; Ps 78:52

Psalm 68:8

¹Lit *This is Sinai* which

^aEx 19:18; Judg 5:4; 2 Sam 22:8; Ps 77:18; Jer 10:10

^bJudg 5:4; Ps 18:9; Is 45:8

^cEx 19:18; Judg 5:5

Psalm 68:9

¹Lit *weary*

^aLev 26:4; Deut 11:11; Job 5:10; Ezek 34:26

Psalm 68:10

^aPs 65:9; 74:19; 78:20; 107:9

Psalm 68:11

¹Lit *word*

^aEx 15:20; 1 Sam 18:6

Psalm 68:12

^aJosh 10:16; Judg 5:19; Ps 135:11

^bJudg 5:30; 1 Sam 30:24

Psalm 68:13

¹Lit *If*

²Or *cooking stones* or *saddle bags*

^aGen 49:14; Judg 5:16

Psalm 68:14

¹Lit *in it*

^aJosh 10:10

^bJudg 9:48

Psalm 68:15

¹Or *mighty mountain is*

^aPs 36:6

Psalm 68:16

^aDeut 12:5; Ps 87:1, 2; 132:13

^bPs 132:14

Psalm 68:17

¹Lit *twice ten thousand*

²Another reading is *The Lord came from Sinai into the sanctuary*

^a2 Kin 6:17; Hab 3:8

^bDeut 33:2; Dan 7:10

Psalm 68:18

¹Heb *YAH*

^aPs 7:7; 47:5; Eph 4:8

^bJudg 5:12

Psalm 68:19

^aPs 55:22; Is 46:4

^bPs 65:5

Psalm 68:20

¹Heb *YHWH*, usually rendered *LORD*

²I.e. in view of; lit *for*

^aPs 106:43

^bDeut 32:39; Ps 49:15; 56:13

Psalm 68:21

^aPs 110:6; Hab 3:13

Psalm 68:22

¹Or *says*

^aNum 21:33; Amos 9:1-3

Psalm 68:23

¹Some versions render, you may *bathe your foot in blood*

^aPs 58:10

^b1 Kin 21:19; Jer 15:3

Psalm 68:24

¹Lit *goings*

²Lit *in the sanctuary*; or *in holiness*

^aPs 77:13

^bPs 63:2

Psalm 68:25

¹Or *The maidens in the midst*

^a1 Chr 13:8; 15:6; Ps 47:6

^bEx 15:20; Judg 11:34

Psalm 68:26

^aPs 22:22, 23; 26:12

^bDeut 33:28; Is 48:1

Psalm 68:27

¹Or *smallest*

²Or *their ruler*

^aJudg 5:14; 1 Sam 9:21

^bJudg 5:18

Psalm 68:28

¹Some mss read *Command, God*

²Lit *for us*

^aPs 29:11; 44:4

^bIs 26:12

Psalm 68:29

¹Or *From Your temple*

^{a1} Kin 10:10, 25; 2 Chr 32:23; Ps 45:12; 72:10; Is 18:7

Psalm 68:30

¹Lit *of*

^aJob 40:21; Ezek 29:3

^bPs 22:12

^cPs 18:14; 89:10

Psalm 68:31

¹Lit *Cush*

^aIs 19:19, 21

^bIs 45:14; Zeph 3:10

Psalm 68:32

^aPs 102:22

^bPs 67:4

Psalm 68:33

¹Lit *heaven of heavens of old*

²Lit *gives forth*

^aDeut 33:26; Ps 18:10; 104:3

^bDeut 10:14; 1 Kin 8:27

^cPs 46:6

^dPs 29:4

Psalm 68:34

¹Lit *clouds*

^aPs 29:1

^bPs 150:1

Psalm 68:35

¹Or *Awesome is God from your sanctuary*

²Lit *holy places*

^aDeut 7:21; 10:17; Ps 47:2; 66:5

^bPs 29:11; Is 40:29

^cPs 66:20; 2 Cor 1:3

Targum

Psa. 68:1 For praise, of David. A hymn and song. ² God will arise, his enemies will be scattered, and his foes will flee from his presence. ³ Just as the smoke is driven out, they will be driven; just as wax will melt in the presence of fire, the wicked will perish in the presence of God. ⁴ And the righteous will rejoice and exult in the presence of the LORD, and they will rejoice joyfully. ⁵ Give praise in the presence of God, praise his glorious name; magnify the one who sits on his glorious throne in Araboth; Yah is his name; and be glad in his presence. ⁶ Father of the orphans, and judge of widows – such is God in the dwelling place of his holy presence. ⁷ God, who makes matches, joining the solitary to mates; who brought out the house of Israel, who were bound in Egypt; for the correct deeds of their fathers <he redeemed them> in public procession; but Pharaoh and his armies, who refused to let them go, dwelt in thirst. ⁸ O God, when you went forth in a pillar of cloud and in a pillar of fire before your people, when you traveled in the wilderness of Jeshimon forever, when you gave the Torah to your people – ⁹ The earth shook, also the heavens dropped dew in the presence of the LORD; as for this Sinai, its smoke went up like the smoke of a furnace before the LORD, God of Israel, was manifested upon it. ¹⁰ When the house of Israel heard the voice of your power, their souls flew away; at once he made to descend upon them the dew of resurrection; O God, you brought the favorable rain to your inheritance, and you supported the assembly which was exhausted. ¹¹ You caused your vigor to go back to it; you appointed a troop of angels to do good to the poor of God. ¹² The LORD gave the words of Torah to his people; truly, Moses and Aaron [were] proclaiming the word of God to the great army. ¹³ Kingdoms with their armies went into exile from their palaces, and the wise were exiled from their knowledge; but the assembly of Israel divides the spoil from heaven. ¹⁴ <The God of Israel said:> If you wicked kings lay down among the rubbish heaps, the assembly of Israel, likened to a dove flying in the clouds of glory, divides the spoil of the Egyptians – silver that is refined, and her treasures full of pure gold. [ANOTHER TARGUM: If you wicked kings sleep in the theatres, which are likened to rubbish heaps, behold, the sons of the assembly of Israel, which are likened to the wings of a dove, are covered with the words of Torah, which are likened to silver, and her scholars, which are likened to the pinions of a young dove in pure gold.] ¹⁵ When she spread her hands over the sea in prayer, Shaddai abased kingdoms, and on her account clouded over Gehinnom like snow; he delivered them from the shadow of death. [ANOTHER TARGUM: Because of this, when the priests spread their hands and bless the people of Israel, Shaddai agrees with them and kings are subdued beneath them; and because of their merits, their sins are made white as snow, and Gehinnom is cooled for the wicked who have received punishment in their children and have repented of their bad deeds.] ¹⁶ Mount Moriah, the place where the patriarchs worshipped in the presence of the LORD, was chosen for the building of the sanctuary; and Mount Sinai for the giving of Torah; Mount Mathnan, Mount Tabor,

and Carmel were disqualified, and a hump was made for them like Mount Mathnan. [ANOTHER TARGUM: Mount Moriah was chosen first for the worship of the patriarchs in the presence of the LORD, and was chosen second for the building there of the sanctuary; and Mount Sinai was pulled up from there and chosen third for the Torah; Mount Buthnin was removed and set far away; Mount Tabor – a miracle was performed there for Barak and Deborah; Mount Carmel – miracles were performed there for Elijah the prophet. And they were racing, one against the other, and arguing one with the other. One said, “On me the presence shall abide,” and the other would say, “On me the presence will abide.” And the Lord of the World, who sharpens the proud and rebellious with the humble, struck them down and they were disqualified. A hump was made for them like Mount Buthnin.] ¹⁷ God said, Why do you leap, O mountains? It is not my will to give the Torah on proud, contemptuous mountains. Behold, Mount Sinai which is humble; the word of the LORD desires to place his presence upon it; [but] in the highest heaven the LORD will abide forever. ¹⁸ The chariots of God are two myriads of burning fire, two thousand angels guiding them; the presence of the LORD rests on them, on the mountain of Sinai, in holiness. ¹⁹ You ascended to the firmament, O prophet Moses; you captured captives, you taught the words of Torah, you gave gifts to the sons of men, and even the stubborn who are converted turn in repentance, [and] the glorious presence of the LORD God abides upon them. ²⁰ Blessed be the LORD, every day he weighs us down, adding commandments to commandments; the mighty one, who is our redemption and our helper forever. ²¹ God is for us might and redemption; and from God the LORD death and loss of breath are inflicted on the wicked through suffocation. ²² Truly, God will break the heads of his enemies, he will make fall out the hair of the man who keeps walking in his sins. ²³ The LORD says, “I will bring back the righteous who have died and been eaten by wild beasts from Buthnin; I will bring back the righteous who have drowned in the depths of the sea.” ²⁴ So that they will see the punishment of the wicked, they will dip their feet in the blood of the slain; the tongue of the wild beast will grow fat from their plumpness, some of them will be sated on the enemies. ²⁵ The house of Israel has seen the paths of your presence on the sea, O God; they say, “The paths of God, king of all the world in holiness!” ²⁶ They rose up early and uttered a song after Moses and Aaron who were playing melodies before them, in the midst of the righteous women who were with Miriam playing timbrels. ²⁷ In the midst of the assemblies, bless God, exalt the LORD, O fetuses in the bellies of their mothers, O seed of Israel! ²⁸ There Benjamin, least of the tribes, who first of all went into the sea — because of this, he received kingship; and after them went down the princes of Judah; the tribes stoned them with stones, and they received dominion after them; the princes of Zebulun were their merchants, and the princes of Naphtali were their warriors. ²⁹ God has commanded your strength; be strong, O God, abide in this sanctuary you have made for us! ³⁰ From your temple you will accept sacrifices; your presence abides on Jerusalem; from their palaces the kings will bring to you sacrifices. ³¹ Rebuke the armies

of sinners, shatter them like reeds, the assembly of warriors who trust in calves, the idols of the Gentiles. His favor is toward the people who are occupied willingly in the Torah, which is purer than silver. Scatter the peoples who desire to wage war! ³² The children of Ham, the Osmani(?), will come from Egypt to be converted; the children of Cush will run to spread their hands in prayer before God. ³³ O kingdoms of the earth, sing praise in the presence of the LORD, sing praise to the LORD forever. ³⁴ To the one who sits on his throne in the heaven of heavens; in the beginning he, by his command, gave through his voice the voice of the spirit of prophecy to the prophets. ³⁵ Ascribe the glory of strength to God, whose excellence is over Israel, and whose strength is in heaven. ³⁶ Fearful is God, from your sanctuary; the mighty one of Israel has given strength and might to his people. Blessed be God!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The theme of this Psalm is the Revelation at Mount Sinai. Israel emerged from this event as the Chosen People of the LORD. At Mount Sinai, the people agreed to be the LORD's people by following His laws. The Ten Commandments is a treaty between God and the people. The LORD would protect the people as long as they followed the Torah. Midrash says that every Jewish soul, past, present, and future, was at Sinai for this event. Therefore, Jews today were at Sinai and must keep the covenant because they were a part of it.

Unfortunately, the world's nations became jealous of Israel both then and now. The world's nations have tried to snuff the Hebrew people out for centuries. However, the LORD promised that a remnant of the people would always remain. From the time of Abraham to the present, the LORD has been with His Chosen People. The dark times of the Babylonian Exile and the Holocaust damaged Israel but never eliminated them. The LORD ensured that the nation was rebuilt every time.

Due to the length of the Psalm, only the spiritual awareness of verses will be explored.

Superscript

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory, by David, a Psalm, a song.

Verse two

The lawless are the nations and people who do not want to follow the Torah of the LORD. The LORD will eventually destroy these nations.

But even as smoke, slowly fading, blows away, even as wax melts before the fire, so the lawless shall perish before the presence of God.

Verse four

Even though Israel is the Chosen People, the LORD commands them to show the world what it means to be a people of God. Therefore, they will want to become a part of the covenant. A view of being the Chosen People is that this nation is to bring the LORD's Torah to the world.

Sing to God, sing praises to His Name, soar up to Him Who guides worlds through barrenness by His Name, and exult greatly before his countenance.

Verse seven

The LORD revealed His power to Israel by leading them from Egypt to Sinai as a cloud during the day and a fire at night.

Thus, O God, when You went forth before Your people, when You marched through the wilderness. Meditate on this verse.

Verse thirteen

Scripture often uses the dove as an allegory of the Jewish nation. In this verse, the dove is in flight, spreading her wings to capture the bright sun's light. Israel always tries to capture the presence of the LORD. It attempts to hear the commandments and directions coming from Heaven.

O, would that you were to remain quietly among the rows of vessels! Even the wing of the dove is covered with silver, and its pinions with sharp gold.

Verse nineteen

The Psalmist writes that the LORD daily bears the burdens of Israel. Israel has been under constant pressure from the world's nations ever since Jacob moved the family to Egypt. The nations of the world desire a closer walk with the LORD but do not follow His Torah and the words of the prophets. It is not an easy life being a devoted Jew. However, in the end, it is more than worth the difficulties.

Blessed be my Master day by day; may He give us a burden to bear. Even the same God is also our Salvation. Meditate on this verse.

Verse twenty-two

“Bashan symbolizes that which is exalted in the flesh, which God's people will conquer as they make their way toward the rest of God. The elect have labored for many centuries in the bondage of spiritual ambition. God will bring His chosen people

from the bondage of sin and self-will and establish them on Mount Zion, the place of their true inheritance.”¹

My Master has promised it; I shall bring you back from Bashan, I will bring you back from the shadowy depths of the sea.

Verse thirty-two

The LORD will make His presence known to all the nations of the earth who turn back to Him.

O kingdoms of the earth, sing to God, sing praises to my Master. Meditate on this verse.

¹ <http://www.wor.org/book/3681/the-mountains-of-bashan>. Accessed December 31, 2022.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

